

Effect of load and speed during downhill walking on salivary Immunoglobulin A

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Abstract: Carrying load is a demanding task involving strenuous physical activity. Downhill load carriage is a part of the daily activity schedule of many individuals. Immunoglobulin A (IgA) is considered as a potential stress marker but not yet fully explored in the downhill load carriage activity. The present study aimed to assess the effect of walking at different speeds with various intensities of load at various downhill gradients on salivary IgA concentration.

Twelve healthy and physically active military personnel walked with various intensities of load at downhill gradients in two walking speeds (2. 5km.h⁻¹ and 4. 0km.h⁻¹) for 36 mins in separate experiments. The salivary samples collected immediately prior to the starting and ending of the exercise sessions were analyzed to find out the changes in sIgA concentration.

The induced stress due to downhill walking led to mixed response in IgA levels when compared to the baseline values. It was observed that there were both an increment and decrement in salivary IgA concentration at various walking speeds and carrying different intensities of load.

Changes of salivary Immunoglobulin A (IgA) showed that downhill walking is also stressful. Observed changes of salivary IgA concentrations in both the walking speeds indicated its role as a positive stress marker in designing work organization.

Practical Implications: The findings of the study may act as a designing tool for planning various training protocols and other work condition not only from the military perspective but for other study populations undergoing physical activity during downhill walking.

Keywords: Downhill walking; Immunoglobulin A; Immune response; Load carriage

1. Introduction

Load carriage maneuver is a crucial element of a military personnel's basic schedule. They are required to carry loads for an extensive period of time in various unfavorable conditions that can include both uphill and downhill walking at different speeds. In addition to this, many local economies, especially in the developing nations, are immensely reliant on manual load carriage. Despite the technological advancements in industrial nations, people still perform many tasks, which, either obligatory or by preference, encompass physical lifting and carrying of load. Military performance may be affected as a result of extreme stress and also be the probable cause of tiredness, altered cognitive abilities, frequent incidences of upper respiratory tract infections (URTI), muscle injury, and painful joint (Booth et al. 2001; Pacque et al. 2002). Exercise stimulates not only the hypothalamic- pituitary- adrenal (HPA) axis but also causes activation of the sympatho-adrenal- medullary (SAM) system (Leal-Cerro et al.

Email corresponding Author: sohu_paul@yahoo.co.in | Vol. 1 Issue 1 pp. 12-19

Cite as – Paul S. and Majumdar D (2022). Effect of load and speed during downhill walking on salivary Immunoglobulin A. *International Journal of Design and Allied Sciences*, 1 (1), 12-19.

2003). It was suggested by Allgrove et al. (2008) that salivary Immunoglobulin A (sIgA) acts as the primary line of defense against infection in the mucosal surfaces and possibly a quantitative and sensitive indicator of the activity of the sympathoadrenal medullary system. It has been observed that very intense physical activity may cause suppression of several immune factors including sIgA. It was first reported by Tomasi et al. (1982) that there was a reduction in sIgA level in volunteers who performed cross country skiing.

Military personnel are frequently exposed to various combinations of stressors especially in operations which are often prolonged, hard, and exhaustive (Opstad 1991; Guezennec et al. 1994). Epidemiological studies have reported that there was a rise in the rate of infection, especially URTIs, after severe physical stress such as in marathon or ultramarathon runs (Nieman et al. 1990; Peters and Bateman 1983). Many other observations for various sports events support this evidence (Gleeson et al. 2000; MacKinnon et al. 1989; MacKinnon et al. 1993). Secretory IgA is considered to be the major immunoglobulin in the mucosal system that provides resistance to respiratory tract infections (Gomez-Merino et al. 2003). A reduction in the concentration of sIgA has been suggested as an indicator of extreme training (Gleeson 2000). Furthermore, Gleeson (2000) suggested that sIgA reduction could facilitate the identification of athletes who are more susceptible to or are at an increased probability of developing respiratory illness. Gomez-Merino et al. (2003) observed decreased IgA levels in French military personnel who did physical training for 3 weeks followed by combat training for 5 days and carrying backpacks of 11 kg. These researchers concluded that an extended and repetitive exercise for instance those included in the schedule of training military personnel induces impairment of the immune system through a diminished mucosal immunity (i.e. decreased sIgA levels). In contrast, a report showed no effect of moderate exercise (running at 50-80% VO_2 max for 15-45 minutes) on total salivary IgA level, suggesting that a probable key factor in determining the IgA response to exercise is the intensity of exercise (McDowell et al. 1991).

Eccentric exercise has been employed as a paradigm to study about tissue injury and the subsequent repair response (Brown et al. 1997). In the field of exercise immunology, immunoglobulins have obtained quite a little attention. There is scanty research till date which report responses of immunoglobulin to varied intensities of exercise especially during downhill walking combined with load carriage and varying speeds. Mckune et al. (2006) observed that two 60 minutes session of downhill running with a gap of 14 days had no significant effect on serum IgA concentration. The present study aimed to investigate whether walking added with different loads and speeds at various downhill gradients had a significant influence on salivary IgA concentration.

2. Methodology

2.1. Participants

Twelve healthy infantry soldiers of the Indian Army volunteered for the study. They were given detailed information about the experimental protocols and prerequisites for volunteering in the study which was given approval by the Institutional ethical committee. Before participation, all the volunteers gave their signed consent. They were all investigated for no indication of injuries, infections, cardiovascular complications and not taking alcohol or any doping agents. They were also asked to refrain from vigorous exercise the day prior to the testing session.

Before the start of the study protocols, the weight and height of all the participants were measured in the morning with nominal clothing by means of an electronic stadiometer (Seca 763 Digital Column Scale) according to the standardized protocol. Personal information like age (27.1 ± 3.6 yrs), height (170.3 ± 4.0 cm), weight (66.2 ± 6.4 kg), army rank and work experience (7.7 ± 3.9 yrs) were acquired from all the participants prior to the beginning of the experiment.

2.2. The various Loads, Speeds and Gradients used in the experiment

The army personnel walked unloaded (NL) and also carried 10.7 kg, 17 kg and 21.4kg loads in the Existing load carriage ensemble (ELCE) of the Indian Army. These loads in combination with two speeds ($2.5 \text{ km} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and $4.0 \text{ km} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) and six decremental gradients (25%, 20%, 15%, 10%, 5% and 20%) simulated in a treadmill were used to generate the various experimental trials.

2.3. *Experimental protocols*

The downhill walking trials were performed under managed laboratory settings with temperature and relative humidity ranging from 25-28°C and 35-40% respectively. The volunteers participating in the study on the respective day of the experiment reported to the laboratory in the morning after having breakfast. The participants were all permitted to rest for an hour before the commencement of the experiment. All the participants were habituated to treadmill walking at various conditions. For the experimental purpose, they were given instructions to walk at two speeds (2.5 km h⁻¹ and 4.0 km h⁻¹) with no load (NL) and carrying various intensities of loads at decreasing gradients (in %) 25, 20, 15, 10, 5, and 0. The participants had to walk for 6 mins for each of the six downhill gradients thus, a total of 36 min walk had to be completed for every experimental condition. All the experimental trials were performed on different days and in random order to circumvent any biasness. A detailed description of the various methodological procedures like the combination of experimental loads and speed, collection of saliva and measurement of IgA and total protein concentration can be obtained from our previous publication (Paul et al. 2015).

2.4. *Collection of saliva and IgA estimation*

The volunteers were asked to abstain from the consumption of any foodstuff and beverage one hour prior to the starting of the experimental trials. The cotton swab method was used to collect the salivary samples for analysis. All the participants chewed the cotton swab at a rate of 1chew/ sec for the duration of 1 minute. The salivary specimens were then taken into centrifuge tubes just before and after the end of each experimental trial session. The collected salivary samples were centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 g and at room temperature and then stored at -80 °C until analyzed further. These salivary samples to be analyzed were at first thawed and then the concentration of sIgA was assessed by sandwich ELISA. The sIgA level was estimated by the DRG salivary IgA ELISA kit (DRG Diagnostics, Marburg, Germany) according to the instruction from the manufacturer. The Bicinchoninic acid (BCA) method was utilized for estimating the total protein concentration, and the standard used was bovine serum albumin (Smith et al., 1985). 25 mL of the salivary sample was added to BCA working reagent of an amount of 200 mL in a microtiter plate consisting of 96 wells. The working reagent was prepared by adding 50 mL of BCA to 1 mL of copper sulfate pentahydrate (4%) solution. At 37°C, the 96 well microtiter plate was incubated for 30 min and the absorbance was assessed at 562 nm.

2.5. *Analysis of the data and statistics*

The sIgA concentrations were represented as mean±SEM (standard error of mean). For statistically analysing the data obtained, four magnitudes of load carriage (NL, 10.7 kg, 17 kg and 21.4 kg) and two speeds (2.5 km.h⁻¹ and 4 km.h⁻¹) combinations were assigned as separate trials and therefore eight individual trials were generated. The concentration of IgA was analysed at 0th minute (Pre-exercise) and at 36th minute (Post exercise). Therefore, the study had two independent variables viz. trial and time. The time was having two levels and trial was having eight levels. Therefore, a total of sixteen (8 X 2) different experimental treatments were generated for the study purpose. The statistical analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 19.0. To find out the effect of various combinations of trial and time on sIgA concentration a two-way repeated measure analysis of variance (ANOVA) was computed and post-hoc analysis was performed by Bonferroni test. The values at P<0.05 level was regarded as significant.

3. Results

3.1. *Effect of load, speed and gradient on Salivary Immunoglobulin A (IgA) concentration*

All the subjects completed all the trials. The response of IgA to downhill walking was a mixed response. It was observed that the concentration of IgA increased while walking unloaded at both the speeds and also while carrying

10.7 kg at 2.5kmhr⁻¹. While carrying higher loads the IgA concentration decreased [Table 1]. The results obtained showed that walking with 17kg and 21.4 kg load at 2.5 kmhr⁻¹ lead to 5.7% and 9.3% reduction in IgA concentration respectively. While walking at 4kmhr⁻¹ and carrying load of 10kg, 17kg and 21.4kg there was a 19.8%, 37.3% and 39.7% decrease of IgA concentration. A significant trial x time interaction effect [F(7, 77)= 2.170,p= 0.046, p<0.05] was observed [Fig. 1a. and 1b.].

Table 1: Mean (SEM) values of IgA concentration changes during pre and post exercise sessions.

Parameter	Speed (kmhr ⁻¹)	Condition	Load (kg)			
			NL	10.7	17	21.4
IgA (ng/ml/mg of protein)	2.5	Pre-exercise	34.9 (4.5)	25.3 (3.6)	30.8 (3.2)	32.0 (7.4)
		Post exercise	38.8 (6.2) *	28.6 (3.1)*	29.0 (3.0) *	29.0 (4.0)*
		% change	11.1	13.3	-5.7	-9.3
	4.0	Pre-exercise	32.8 (4.4)	31.1 (4.3)	28.5 (4.4)	33.4 (5.5)
		Post exercise	35.0 (6.0)*	25.0 (2.4)*	17.9 (3.1)*	20.2 (4.0)*
		% change	11.1	-19.8	-37.3	-39.7

Figure 1a. Effects of load carriage on changes in sIgA concentration (ng/ml/mg of protein) while downhill walking at 2.5 kmhr⁻¹ during pre and post exercise sessions.

Fig 1b. Effects of load carriage on changes in sIgA concentration (ng/ml/mg of protein) while downhill walking at 4 kmhr^{-1} during pre and post exercise sessions.

4. Discussion

The present investigation was undertaken to identify the alterations in salivary IgA concentration during downhill load carriage walking, each of 36 minutes duration with various combinations of loads and speeds. The data obtained from the study showed that during walking at downhill gradients unloaded (NL) and carrying load of 10.7kg the IgA concentration increased at 2.5 kmhr^{-1} . At 4 kmhr^{-1} walking speed, IgA concentration increased for NL condition. For all the remaining trials IgA concentration significantly decreased.

Although physical activity has numerous health benefits till date majority of the studies report that strenuous exercise can temporarily suppress immunity. sIgA has been identified as one of the key components in providing resistance to various microorganisms in the mouth (Mackinnon 1996). Various studies have delineated the fact that physical activity which are stressful viz. cycling for 2 hours at a maximal oxygen consumption of 70-75% (Mackinnon and Jenkins 1993), running marathons (Muns et al. 1989) led to reduced concentration of sIgA. The present study delineates that when the subjects walked at downhill gradients at the lower speed of 2.5 kmhr^{-1} IgA concentration increased during walking without any load and carrying 10.7kg but when the participants walked with 17kg and 21.4kg load IgA concentration started decreasing. At 4 kmhr^{-1} walking speed, IgA concentration increased only when walking without load but reduced while carrying load magnitudes of 10.7kg, 17kg and 21.4kg. Therefore, it was observed that walking at downhill gradients with 4 kmhr^{-1} speed and carrying only 10.7 kg becomes stressful for the military personnel. There was around 20%, 37% and 40% decrease of salivary IgA levels while carrying loads of 10.7 kg, 17kg and 21.4kg respectively at 4 kmhr^{-1} walking speed.

The observations on the concentration of sIgA in the current study is also in support with the above cited studies but is contradicting the observations of other studies that have either shown no change (Bishop et al. 2000) or an increment in sIgA concentration (Blannin et al. 1998; Ramezani et al. 2012) during stressful conditions. These variations in the result of salivary IgA concentration is dependent on the age and fitness level (Niemann et al. 2006), level of hydration of the subject (Walsh et al. 2004), type of physical activity (Blannin et al. 1998), and the magnitude of stress persuaded by that form of activity (Gleeson and Pyne 2000) as well as the period of the activity (Ramezani et al. 2012). Further, Campbell and Turner (2018) concluded that exercise may most probably improve immune competency across the lifetime of an individual. Even though the physiological processes involved in the reduction of the sIgA level are not clearly known but results from different investigations suggest that when the sympathetic nervous system (SNS) gets stimulated due to vigorous physical activity, it leads to vasoconstriction of the blood vessels especially the arteries supplying the salivary glands. This event leads to the hindrance of transferring IgA from their site of production viz. the lymphocyte B cells to the sub-mucosal areas of the mouth cavity thereby leading to a diminished IgA concentration (Mackinnon 1999). Furthermore, Wira and Rossoll (1991)

reported that the levels of sIgA declined significantly owing to the repositioning of polymeric IgA from the mucosa to the circulation regulated by glucocorticoids but this converse correlation is not detected every time.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the data reported herein provide evidence that a single bout of submaximal acute exercise generally decreases the IgA concentration in healthy human subjects. Although it has been reported that downhill walking is physiologically less stressful, but when combined with various magnitudes of load it becomes strenuous and may lead to a decreased salivary IgA concentration. The response pattern of sIgA during the different intensities of exercise trials similar to combat military operations followed in this study will help in designing precautionary measures and may also diminish the susceptibility of military forces from Upper respiratory tract illness during combat performance and various training programs. sIgA can be regarded as a stress marker with downhill load carriage experiment where higher degree of load combined with downhill grades and speeds shows a positive response with respect to incidences of URTI. It can therefore be considered for necessary work design. However, present study is limited to 12 subjects with only 5 downhill gradients (-25%, -20%, -15%, -10%, -5%, 0%) and two walking speeds (2.5kmhr⁻¹ and 4kmhr⁻¹). Another limitation of the study is the age group and the gender because this study was conducted in male, extremely fit Indian soldiers with an age group of 27.1±3.6 yrs. Furthermore, the oral health status of the volunteers was also not evaluated as IgA concentration variation is also dependent on it. Future experiments can be designed for various age groups in the normal population and female volunteers can be included to assess whether there is the same effect as that obtained in the present study.

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